

Research as a Veritable Tool for Enhancing Students' Learning Experiences in the 21st Century University Education: Counselling Implications

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Abstract

The study sought to find out specifically how research by students enhances learning experiences of university undergraduates. The design of the study was descriptive survey design. Three research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. 250 out of 400 final year undergraduates of faculties of education in two universities in Abia State constituted the sample size for the study. Purposive sampling technique by balloting was used to select the sample for the study. A questionnaire titled Research for Enhancing Learning Experiences (RELE) was used for data collection. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used for data analysis. Findings of the study showed that research by students enhances learning experiences by stimulating to a very great extent the spirit of independent learning among students. The results also indicated that students' research to a great extent facilitates openness towards learning new things among students. The study equally showed that there was no significant gender difference on the extent research by students enhances their learning experiences. Based on the findings, conclusion, discussions, implications and recommendations were made. It was recommended that lecturers should be encouraged to be giving students opportunities to be carrying out research in their various course contents or areas of study from time to time through assignments, seminar presentations and others.

Keywords: Research, Students, Learning experiences, 21st century education, Counselling

Introduction

Research is a veritable tool when it comes to educational enterprise. Research is a combination of experiences and reasoning; a systematic study of a problem with a view to advance the fronts of human knowledge which is what education enterprise entails (Emaikwu, 2011). Research involves inquiry. It has to do with digging to pass those known facts and reaching to the unknown. Eric (2009) related that research is the process of systematic inquiring by which

the human kind measures how things are, why things are the way they are and how they could be improved. Research is concerned with discovering new facts, correcting misconceptions, interpreting ambiguous conclusions based on identified accurate knowledge. Bell, Cadidiguly and Davis (2010) opined that research also deals with modifying, revising or verifying accepted conclusions or theories based on new information. The authors further explained that research could take the form of finding solutions to assignments given, writing and presentation of seminar papers or a problem situation. Kerlinger in Ali (2006) defined research as the systematic objective and accurate search for the solution to a problem that involves data collection, analysis and reporting.

When one is given a problem solving situation he goes into search to systematically, objectively and accurately get to the solution. Ali (2006) also defined research as investigation activities directed towards the collection of analysis and interpretation of data that leads to the development of organized body of knowledge. Thus, when students are given sub-themes of lecture topics to study under organized small groups discussions, debates, competition, assignments or seminar presentation, they go into investigative activities that could lead them to developing new knowledge. The purpose of research therefore is to identify, explain, discover, control and predict human knowledge on some issues and problems leading to acquisition of permanent knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. Emaikwu (2011) seems to sum up the goal of research as to discover and learn accurate facts on which appropriate and responsive interpretations and explanations could be based for improved learning.

In the context of this study, research is a reliable means of finding facts, testing ideas and proposals that increase learning experiences. The research by students involves exposing the students to opportunities for getting latest advancement and innovations in their various areas of study for easier acquisition of knowledge and skills for better adaptation and adjustment in the present world of work. This can be done through regular assignments and seminar writing and presentation. Others include organized small group discussions, debates, competitions and problems solving situations (NTI, 1996). Regular assignment covers individual and group take-home assignments. When such takes place, majority of the students go all out to research for materials that could provide likely answers to the assignments, select the most necessary ones and explain in writing for presentation or submission. In this way, students are opportune to become efficient learners and study outside the classroom (Jottos, 2007) it equally creates avenue for independent and active self-regulated learning. Thus they become managers of their own, learning experiences. Cognitive psychologists such as Zimmerman, (2000), Eze, (2003), Li and Chun, (2012) asserted that efficient; learners actively self-regulate their behaviours and pursue learning in an independent, active and deliberate manner. Schunk and Zimmerman, earlier posited that learners who take part in the learning process effectively (regularly doing assignments, writing and presenting seminar papers, debates, group discussions, leading them to asking and answering questions and getting feedback from the teachers are effective in the management of their learning experiences. Hence they become motivated, independent and meta-cognitively active in learning process. This means that giving students feedback on their assignments is vital in enhancing learning experiences.

Seminar presentation involves giving the students sub-themes of course contents after introduction by the lecturer to come up sometime with individual or group write-ups or papers in form of mini project and present orally to the entire class. This can make students to go into the process of research which includes collecting (necessary materials), analyzing, interpreting data, concluding and referencing. Through it, students could learn how to do current referencing of other people's works. It exposes students to educational facilities and resources such as libraries, bookshops, resource centres, textbooks, journals, internet browsing for academic activities (Obi, 2015) instead of flocking the internet for social activities. It promotes independent learning and openness to learning new things according to Dabbah and Skitaintas, (2012). Students in this way are also made to use more learning strategies and thus become proficient learners (Lai, 2009). Fottos (2007) opined that regular assignments help students to discover areas of interests and create avenues for learning individually outside the classroom.

In the process of writing seminar papers, some students have been known to have come across topics they eventually used as titles for project writing in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor's degree; students may not only come closer to different learning materials but also interact more constructively with colleagues and lecturers for clarification and direction. Thus, students are made busy and have less time available for social activities with the social networking sites (SNSs) that consume time for personal academic activities these days.

Organized small group discussions, debates and competition encourage learners to develop areas of interest that make for meaningful learning. Robinson (2008) opined that organized small group discussions, debates and competitions are also means of ideal meaningful learning. Problem solving situations help students learn more by challenging their thoughts or creative mind (Grandhi, 2009).

Learning is said to be a permanent change in behavior due to experience. It refers to gaining knowledge, skills, attitudes or behavior by studying or from being taught. Students gain knowledge when they are taught by teachers and add to their knowledge through studying outside the classroom. Hence, the word enhancing here refers to adding to or increasing the knowledge gained abinitio. Shanhan in NTI (1996), conceptualized learning as a process which produces series of changes in human knowledge, skills and values that ultimately make the learner change behavior permanently Meconnelm, steer and Owens (2003) defined learning as a continuous process in which knowledge and skills are acquired.

Enhancing the learning experiences of students in the 21st century university education who prefer exploring social media for social activities to academic activities means that the lecturers have to stimulate them adequately by exposing them to different effective ways of learning such as creating avenue for them to learn outside the classroom, independent or self regulated learning, challenging their thoughts for more new learning and developing areas of interest in learning. The researchers are interested in finding out the extent regular assignment and seminar writing and presentation by students stimulate the spirit of independent learning and openness to learning new things respectively. When university students these days are made

to learn in these ways, they will not only be helped to appeal to all their senses for improved learning but also minimize the defects of lecture method which appeals to auditory sense alone. The lecture method which is the process whereby the lecturer stands before the students and verbally delivers a pre-planned body of knowledge to students is more of teacher-centred and less learner centred especially in this 21st century university education. Lecture method does no longer add to the growth of students' learning or creative mind. It is increasingly making students passive learners. Raine (2011) reported that students of 21st century education are characterized by digital age. They prefer multitasking and non-linear access to information (MacCarty, 2010). Obi (2015) related that the students have low tolerance for lecture and prefer active rather than passive learning in their various educational levels.

Education is the process of equipping individuals with the necessary skills and attitudes that could help them function effectively in the society. The different levels of education in Nigeria are pre-primary, primary, secondary and Tertiary education of which university education is one. University education is the education that is acquired in the university after secondary education. The recipients of university education in their 100 to 400 or 500 levels are called undergraduates or university students without gender bias. In this study, undergraduates and university students are used interchangeably to mean male and females students in universities. University education is for training for higher level of manpower needs (Eya, Adiewere & Eya, 2015). Taking one's mind to years before now, university education used to be for students who are academically inclined hence we have senior secondary education for only those students who are academically inclined for proceeding to universities while those who are technically inclined proceed to technical or vocational institutions or centres such as the polytechnics and mono-technics or apprenticeship centres. Unfortunately, the 21st century university education is housing students of varied inclinations partly because all have realized the role of university education in satisfying the earnings of parents and partly because there are no white collar jobs for secondary school graduates. These days, universities are filled to the brim with large student population; some are there to fill the existing vacancies with little or no interest in studies. Some are constantly flocking the internet for group chats, uploading of pictures and telling stories while some cluster around the lecture halls pretending to be listening while the lecturer is inside verbalizing pre-prepared body of knowledge to students. And with decayed infrastructural facilities and resources majority of the students are finding it very difficult to understand through lecture method of teaching. Bankole (2012) posited that infrastructure and other learning facilities in the universities are decaying in an alarming rate. This study focused on finding out a teaching strategy that could substantially improve the learning experiences of students in this 21st century university education which could in turn improve the quality of university graduates that is increasingly on the decline as suggested by Oyewole (2009).

Statement of the Problem

University education in the 21st century is facing numerous challenges, one of which is quality of graduates that is in the decline. Many people attribute the low quality of graduates to

the lecture method of teaching undergraduates. The undergraduates now need a strategy of teaching them that would expose them to discover, explain and interpret knowledge through which their thoughts could be challenged, auditory and visual senses are appealed to. Evidence from literature tends to suggest that research by students in form of involvement in regular assignments, seminar writing and presentation, organized small group discussion, debates, competitions and problem solving situations have the potential of enhancing students learning experiences; hence the need for the study to find out the extent research by students themselves could enhance their learning experiences in the 21st century university education and to highlight its implication for counseling.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to find out the extent to which students' research enhances their learning experiences. Specifically, the study sought to find out the following;

1. the extent regular assignment stimulates spirit of independent learning among undergraduates.
2. the extent seminar presentation facilitates openness towards learning new things among undergraduates.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does regular assignment stimulate spirit of independent learning among undergraduates?
2. To what extent does seminar presentation facilitates openness towards learning new things among undergraduates?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho: There is no significant gender difference on the extent research by students enhance learning experiences among undergraduates.

Method

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. According to Emaikwu (2011), descriptive survey involves gathering of information about a large population of people by sampling the entire population. The study was carried out in Abia State. Two education faculties of the two universities in Abia State were involved in the study. Abia state is one of the states in South-East geo-political zone of Nigeria with its capital at Umuahia. There are two main universities in Abia State- one state and one federal. The population of the study was 400 final year undergraduates of the faculties of education in the two universities in Abia State. The sample for the study was made up of 250 comprising 100 males and 150 females undergraduates from the education faculties of the universities selected using purposive sampling technique of balloting. The sample was made up of students who are in their final years and must have been involved in assignments and seminars more than other undergraduates in 100 to 300 levels.

Moreover, they are the undergraduates that are presently carrying out project writing in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor's degree in Education (B.ED). They have also spent not less than 4 years in the universities. It was assumed that they would participate out of interest and ability. 250 represents 63% of the population which is allowed in a research of this nature according to Ali (2006) and Uzoagulu, (2011).

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled Research for Enhancing Learning Experiences (RELEQ). The instrument has 3 clusters: A, B and C. Cluster A housed the bio-data of the respondents while Clusters B and C contain 10 items each according to the two research questions that guided the study. The items were patterned in a 4-point rating scale of very great extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The real limits of the numbers were used. Thus, 3.00 to 4.00 means Very Great Extent (VGE), 2.00 to 2.99 means Great Extent (GE), 1.00 to 1.99 means Low Extent (LE), -1 to -1.99 means very low extent (VLE). The face validity of the instrument was determined by giving the initial copy to three research experts in Educational management and planning, psychology and Measurement and Evaluation, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The research experts looked at the items in terms of suitability, accuracy, language construction and others. Their corrections, criticisms and suggestions were effected and reflected in the final copy of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using test-re-test method, in which 20 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 20 undergraduates of University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State faculty of Education on two occasions of two weeks interval. After computation using pearson product moment correlation co-efficient procedure, reliability/stability values of 0.87 and 0.78 were obtained respectively.

The questionnaire instrument (RELEQ) was administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of a research assistant. 250 copies of the RELEQ were administered and 250 were collected on the spot. This helped in getting 100% return of the questionnaire. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions but t-test statistical tool was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion for rejecting or not rejecting the hypothesis was: reject H_0 if t-calculated value was higher than the t-critical value and do not reject H_0 if t-calculated value was less than t-critical value.

Results

The results of the study are presented below:

Research Question 1: How do regular assignments by students stimulate spirit of independent learning among undergraduates?

Table 1: Analysis of responses on how regular assignments stimulate the spirit of independent learning among undergraduates.

S/ N	ITEM STATEMENT	RESPONSES						DECISION
		VGE	GE	LE	VLE	X	SD	
	Regular assignments have made me to be:							
1.	staying away from people when I am reading to avoid distraction	201 (840)	10 (30)	5 (10)	25 (25)	3.6	0.1	VGE
2.	keeping a dictionary around me for checking meaning of unfamiliar words	181 (724)	57 (171)	2 (4)	10 (10)	3.24	0.07	VGE
3.	putting off my handset for maximum concentration when going through my notes alone.	170 (680)	48 (144)	10 (20)	22 (22)	3.46	0.1	VGE
4.	to always enter into a private corner for revision after lectures.	159 (636)	61 (183)	24 (48)	6 (6)	3.33	0.04	VGE
5.	going to the library to search for textbooks on topics in my course outline	130 (520)	50 (150)	40 (80)	30 (30)	3.12	0.01	VGE
6.	being on a reading table alone to create space for the different books I usually make use of	198 (780)	10 (30)	9 (18)	36 (36)	3.46	0.02	VGE
7.	retiring to a corner after discussing with course mates to memorize points raised.	170 (680)	30 (90)	5 (10)	45 (45)	3.00	0.4	VGE
8.	getting up in the midnight to study previous lecture notes	207 (680)	35 (105)	6 (12)	2 (2)	3.79	0.01	VGE
9.	jotting down points during lectures to enable me write my assignments without ease much difficulties.	196 (780)	11 (33)	20 (40)	24 (24)	3.51	0.03	VGE
10.	Keeping myself busy most of the time generating likely questions and answers for writing my assignments well.	149 (596)	48 (144)	4 (8)	49 (49)	3.19	0.1	VGE

Data on table 1 show that all the items (1-10) have mean scores between 3.19 and 3.79 which are within the real limits of numbers 3.00 to 4.00; indicating Very Great Extent (VGE). The Standard deviation ranges from 0.01 to 0.1. This shows closeness in opinion. Therefore, the data in table 1 reveal that regular assignments stimulate spirit of independent learning among undergraduates by making them to stay alone when reading to avoid distraction (Item1, X=3.00), keeping a dictionary around when reading to check the meaning of unfamiliar words, (Item 2, X=3.24), putting off hand set for maximum concentration when reading alone, (Item 3, X=3.33), revision after lecturers (Item 4, X=3.3), going to library to search for textbooks (Item 5, X=3.12), being on a reading table alone to create space for the use of different textbooks (Item 6, X=3.46), memorizing points raised after each discussion with course mates (Item 7, X=3.00), getting up in midnights to

read previous lecture notes (Item 8, $X=3.79$), jotting down points to help in writing assignments without difficulties (Item 9, $X=3.51$) and keeping oneself busy with generating of likely questions and answers (Item 10, $X=3.19$).

Research Question 2: To what extent does seminar presentation facilitate openness towards learning new things among undergraduates.

Table 2: Analysis of responses on the extent seminar presentation facilitate openness towards learning new things.

S/ N	ITEM STATEMENT	RESPONSES						DECISION
		VGE	GE	LE	VLE	X	SD	
	Seminar presentation has opened my eyes to learning new things such as:							
11.	sources of materials for write ups	101 (404)	72 (222)	27 (54)	50 (50)	2.92	0.13	GE
12.	how to consult library personnel to locate needed textbooks	98 (392)	63 (189)	40 (80)	90 (90)	2.68	0.01	GE
13.	awareness of serial sections of the university library for unrenovable texts.	59 (236)	87 (261)	24 (48)	80 (80)	2.5	0.1	GE
14.	arranging paper presentation electronically	100 (400)	70 (210)	11 (22)	70 (70)	2.81	0.03	GE
15.	oral presentation of write ups within the time limit	120 (480)	50 (150)	10 (20)	70 (70)	2.92	0.02	GE
16.	current style of referencing other people's work	112 (448)	45 (135)	20 (40)	73 (73)	2.78	0.04	GE
17.	how to select topics for projects	107 (426)	22 (66)	39 (78)	82 (82)	2.62	0.07	GE
18.	how to analyze data using statistical tools such as frequencies and mean scores	87 (348)	48 (144)	37 (74)	78 (78)	2.58	0.25	GE
19.	reviewing somebody's work	90 (360)	41 (123)	40 (80)	79 (79)	2.83	0.14	GE

Data on table 2 show all the items (11-20) as having mean scores within the real limit of 2.00 to 2.99; indicating Great Extent (GE). The standard deviation of the items range from 0.01 to 0.14; indicating that the responses are not very far from each other. Therefore, seminar presentation by students facilities to a great extent openness towards learning new things among undergraduates such as discovering sources of material for write-ups (Item 11, $X=2.92$), how to consult library personnel to locate needed textbooks (Item 12, $X=2.64$), awareness of serial sections of university library (Item 13, $X=2.5$), how to arrange paper presentation electronically (Item 14, $X=2.81$) oral presentation of write-ups within time limit (Item 15, $X=2.92$), current style of referencing (Item 16, $X=2.78$), how to select topics for projects (Item 17, $X=2.62$), analyzing data with statistical tools (Item 18, $X=2.58$) and reviewing some body's work (Item 20, $X=2.83$).

Hypothesis Testing:

HO: There is no significant gender difference on the extent research by students enhance learning experiences among under graduates ($P < 0.05$).

Test 3: t-test analysis of significant gender difference on the extent research enhance learning experiences among undergraduates.

Group	N	X	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	100	2.72	1.59	248	0.67	1.96	HO not rejected
Female	150	2.69	1.56				

Not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The result on table 3 show that t-cal value of 0.67 is less than the t-crit of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 2.48 degree of freedom. This indicates that the hypothesis of no significant gender difference on the extent research by students enhances learning experiences among undergraduates is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study as presented in table 1 revealed that research by students in form of involvement in regular assignments stimulates the spirit of independent learning to a very great extent is in agreement with Dabbaah and Kitautal (2012) who asserted that regular assignments promote spirit of independent learning among students. It is also supported by the findings of Fottos (2007) that assignments carried out by students do not only help them discover areas of interests but also create avenue for independent learning outside the classroom. The finding is equally given credence by some cognitive psychologists such as Zimmerman (2000) who related that being personally involved in learning activities such as regular assignments makes students to become efficient learners who actively self regulate their own behaviours and pursue learning in an independent, active and deliberate manner. Specific findings of the study in table one that regular writing of assignments prompts students to use different ways of independent learning such as staying alone, getting up in the midnights to read, reading with a dictionary around, consulting different textbooks and others are in line with Lai (2009) who posited that through regular assignments students are made to device more learning strategies that make them to become proficient learners.

The findings of the study in table two that research in form of seminar writing and presentation by students facilitates to a great extent openness towards learning new things are in line with Emaikwu (2011) who related that the ultimate goal of any aspect of research includes discovery of new knowledge and learning facts on which appropriate and responsive interpretations and explanations are based. The findings are also in agreement with Eric's (2015) assertion that research (even in form of seminar presentation) exposes students to opportunities for getting the latest advancement and innovations. Below (1996) supported the findings of the study by explaining that in the process of writing seminar papers some students have been known to have discovered topics for their final year projects. The findings are equally in line with NTI (1996) and Weisgerber (2010) that presentation of seminar papers exposes students to

educational facilities of both human and material resources such as libraries, bookshops, resource centres, textbooks, journals, personnel and internet browsing for academic activities that keep learners reasonably busy respectively.

The result of the hypothesis testing that male and female respondents do not differ significantly in opinion on the extent research enhances learning experiences among undergraduates is not unexpected. The reason could be that in this digital age, there is hardly a remarkable demarcation between students in the use of their study periods for Social Networking Sites (SNSs) based on gender, so that involving students in research through regular assignments, writing and presentation of course seminar, group discussions, debates and others would keep majority of them so busy that their learning experiences could be enhanced almost at the same extent.

Conclusion

Research in form of regular assignment stimulates spirit of independent learning among undergraduates to a very great extent, seminar presentation facilitates openness towards learning new things to a great extent among undergraduates irrespective of gender. In this way research by students themselves becomes a veritable tool for enhancing students' learning experiences in the 21st century university education.

Counselling Implications

The finding of the study has implications for counselling practice. It is pointing out that counselling personnel in universities should step up their educational guidance and counselling services to helping undergraduate students to maximize their educational potentials through doing assignments and seminars as often as they are given; since they do not only help them to gain scores but also stimulate the spirit of independent learning and expose them to learning and adapting to new innovations in education.

It also implies that counselling should be proactively extended to lecturers on the importance of giving regular individual and group assignments and seminar presentation activities to students in their various areas of specialization. This could be achieved through organizing academic staff forum from time to time.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Lecturers are encouraged to adopt more of research strategy of presenting learning experience to undergraduates.
2. Giving students regular assignments and involving them in seminar writing and presentation should be given top priority among the techniques in the strategy of teaching undergraduates.
3. Educational guidance and counselling services should focus more on importance of assignments and seminar presentation by students.

4. Academic advisers of students should encourage individual students they are taking care of academically to take assignments and seminar presentations very seriously.
5. Lecturers should not be gender biased when giving students assignments and seminar presentations.
6. Every university management should ensure the provision of adequate educational facilities such as equipped libraries, textbooks and journals, bookshops, resource centres and others to enable students explore to enhance their learning experiences.
7. Counselling units of universities should incorporate academic staff forum in their schedule of services to enable lecturers be acquainted with new strategies such as research strategy and techniques that enhance learning experiences of undergraduates.

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